

Abstract

The Open Science philosophy was lately chosen within the European Union as a default paradigm for the publicly funded research. Open Science is to address the data sharing issues, improve the use of public funding and encourage collaboration through better exchange of knowledge. The approach is being implemented by the definition of standards, creation of digital infrastructures and publishing models.

This document works towards the creation of a common e-infrastructure for the Wind Energy community and the other aspects aligned to the European Open Science philosophy. This is achieved by suggesting a set of guidelines and actions for the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) and the Wind Energy community as a whole, addressing legal, standardisation, infrastructure and training aspects of the topic. The results of this work allow making better use of the existing European e-infrastructures, and better planning of ongoing and future projects, inline with the European strategy of Digital Single Market. It will also serve as a starting point for the formulation of the EERA-Wind Open Science strategy.

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Abbreviations

EC - European Commission
ECI - European Cloud Initiative
EERA - The European Energy Research Alliance
E&R - Education and Research
ICT - Information and Communications Technology
IP - Intellectual Property
NDA - Non-Disclosure Agreement
T&C - Terms and Conditions
WP - Work Package
WT - Wind Turbine

1 Introduction

The need for the creation of a common e-infrastructure for Wind Energy is a growing issue. It is an important element of the Open Science philosophy, which is now the default approach for all H2020 projects [9]. Construction of an e-infrastructure is a compulsory element of any project implementing the H2020 Research infrastructure objective [3], which follows guidelines from the advisory groups such as ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures), or e-IRG (e-Infrastructure Reflection Group). ICT infrastructures also form a part of the European Cloud Initiative (ECI) which is to strengthen the data-driven innovation [4] and implements one of the top ten EC priorities - the creation of the Digital Single Market, which is to prepare Europe for the fourth industrial revolution. There are numerous examples of common ICT infrastructures covering needs of a specific community. The best examples for wind energy is the [Seadata.net](#) covering offshore renewables, or [A2e](#) Data Archive and Portal project being now implemented in the US.

In Europe, EERA through projects like IRPWind is the most qualified for leading this type of activities. The vision for the EERA Joint Programme for Wind Energy is to create a “virtual research centre” running an Integrated Research Programme [5] and the IRPWind project is an implementation of that vision. It is only natural that the “virtual research centre” needs a “virtual infrastructure” for facilitating the collaboration.

In the past two decades the wind energy research community have achieved a great improvement in the amount and quality of physical infrastructures (laboratories, experimental parks), databases, and virtual services. The IRPWind project is successfully used for providing access to those facilities for the IRPWind participants. Unfortunately the fragmentation of the research infrastructure is still visible when it comes to the ability to find and understand research data, gain access to it, or ability to perform experiments remotely. In general, there is a lack of EERA policies for data management and a strategy for promoting open-access data sharing through dedicated e-infrastructures, and this project could serve as a starting point for addressing it. The main question to be answered is how the initiatives dealing with the research fragmentation within the wind energy community could be better synchronized with each other, as well as with the general efforts for the creation of the virtual infrastructures within the European Union. This document suggests how this could be achieved through the creation of a common wind energy e-infrastructure, and what steps should be taken towards its creation.

1.1 Scope

E-infrastructure in the European context can be understood in two ways. Firstly, as a set of European level services, which in general are to improve the value for money of EU research, and secondly as a community specific e-infrastructure which facilitates the exchange of data and services within and outside of the community.

The guidelines presented in this document aim to bring the wind energy community closer to the creation of a single common e-infrastructure, as well as to make a better use of the existing european research infrastructure.

1.2 Document organisation

Chapter 2 briefly summarizes the EU policies for open science and e-infrastructures. It also references the available services which can be found in the appendix. Section 2.1 provides example case studies which are currently being implemented as a result of the project.

Chapter 3 presents guidelines for the European wind energy community together with short justification.

2 European e-infrastructures

There are two major initiatives which will be strongly influencing the priorities for research projects in Europe in the coming years. The first is the Open Science philosophy, which puts priority on research sharing and cooperation. To achieve that, more attention is given to publishing, standards, and infrastructures. All the mentioned topics are strongly interrelated and can not be considered separately, thus the scope of this document has been extended outside of the e-infrastructures.

“The European Commission and the Council of the European Union have expressed that they are prepared to take a leading role to facilitate and accelerate the transition towards open science. [...] a multi-actor approach was formulated to reach two important pan-European goals for 2020:

1. Full open access for all scientific publications

This requires leadership and can be accelerated through new publishing models and compliance with standards set.

2. A fundamentally new approach towards optimal reuse of research data

Data sharing and stewardship is the default approach for all publicly funded research. This requires definitions, standards and infrastructures.”

Amsterdam call for action on open science [1]

To support open science, a number of general, pan-European e-infrastructure services are available for European researchers. These are summarised in Appendix [European e-infrastructure services](#). It is worth noting that, while the e-infrastructure services are currently restricted for researchers and to certain degree they are designed to form a complete environment, they are also part of the “Digitising European Industry” package and the Digital Single Market priority. For that reason the European e-infrastructures are expected to go beyond the research community and support the fast changing, commercial, digital environment rather than compete with it. Also an important part of the European Cloud Initiative is interfacing the dynamic market of digital services for the public/research sector.

“The public and private investment needed to implement the **European Cloud Initiative** is estimated at €6.7 billion. The Commission estimates that, overall, €2 billion in Horizon 2020 funding will be allocated to the European Cloud initiative. The estimation of the required additional public and private investment is €4.7 billion in the period of 5 years.”

European Cloud Initiative [4]

These plans should be considered when designing an e-infrastructure for wind energy, by making it prepared for the creation of Digital Single Market for wind energy, as well as keeping it open to the dynamic changes of the ICT technologies. A modern e-infrastructure should be unique for both private and public sector, and it should not be redesigned every couple of years, but rather be able to evolve with the changing environment.

2.1 Case studies for wind energy community

During the project a number of ideas were discussed about how the European e-infrastructure services could address some of the issues within wind energy community. Some of the ideas which have been discussed during this project are presented below.

2.1.1 PRACE

PRACE (Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe) is a pan-European supercomputing research infrastructure, based in 25 member states, that provides access to computing and data management resources and services for large-scale scientific and engineering applications [11]. Currently, the PRACE-MesoWake Project Access counts with 17.7 million cpu-hours to set-up a virtual laboratory for wind energy, based on high fidelity multi-scale modeling of atmospheric flows using large-eddy simulation [12]. With PRACE resources, the project will generate a database of high-fidelity simulations around relevant validation cases for the design of reduced-order engineering models.

2.1.2 EUDAT

The data services provided by [EUDAT](#) have generated interest in two projects: The New European Wind Atlas ([NEWA](#)), the MesoWake [12] project and the ScanFlow (project within the IRPWind Research Infrastructure Joint Experiment program). In the case of NEWA the idea would be to make the NEWA databases part of EUDAT infrastructure, thus gaining experts support, making the results citable and discoverable through the B2FIND [6] service.

The MesoWake LES database can be used in NEWA for the design of RANS models as part of the wind atlas model-chain.

ScanFlow is a High-resolution full-scale wind field measurement campaign of the ECN's 2.5 MW aerodynamic research wind turbine, using DTU's 3D [WindScanner](#) and SpinnerLidar. For ScanFlow, the cooperation with EUDAT would allow storage of low level measurement data which were generated within the IRPWind infrastructure call project. Interest on keeping the data was expressed during the IRPWind 2016 conference, unfortunately the size of data and lack of budget left the problem unsolved. The issue was discussed with EUDAT members who expressed an interest in cooperation and confirmed the ability to store 200TB of lidar measurements free of charge, within the B2FIND service. Finally, data collected through the IRPWind call for experiments can be also made available open-access through EUDAT.

These ideas are awaiting the EUDAT 2017 call for pilot studies. A proposal for a wind energy pilot will explore the potential of using EUDAT services to contribute to the EERA-Wind data management strategy. Case studies using NEWA, ScanFlow, MesoWake and IRPWind data will be used to determine the best way to interact with EUDAT as a research community. Having a collection of heterogeneous databases will allow to discuss data management standards for the EERA e-infrastructure strategy.

2.1.3 Data citation - visibility in OpenAIRE

IRPWind works with a number of data sources, none of which is implementing the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable). An attempt to address that on specific examples have shown gaps in the available solutions, especially when the data are somehow restricted. The current approach of the experimental data providers to the problem is to publish their own conclusions on the experiments first, thus letting the data users to cite the publication in order to acclaim the experiment. At

the same time only some universities are able to register the existence of restricted data stored in their servers and even in those cases the researchers are usually unaware of the possibility.

While not satisfactory, certain steps are being taken towards addressing the issues. Public data providers for benchmarking exercises organised in windbench.net portal, are now being advised to store their data at the ZENODO platform. DTU has been advised to contact the DTU library, which is capable of registering research data (both public and restricted). CENER is discussing with its library the possibility of publishing information stored in winbench portal.

3 Guidelines towards the European e-infrastructures.

3.1 Standardisation

Any infrastructure needs internal standardisation. Standards allow to significantly reduce the effort of using and processing data, and the support needed for its understanding. E-infrastructures, consisting of a number of distributed and interconnected elements, cannot exist without standards defining the method in which they communicate. Databases using different formats cannot be joined by one seamless service, and the lack of standardised metadata prevents efficient data discovery and data mining. Finally, without standardisation it is impossible to develop services which make automatic use of the e-infrastructure.

The problem in wind energy is that there is no centralised source of standards. As a result, more than one file format is often used in parallel, or not all the researchers are aware of the best available solutions. EERA is in a unique position of having access to experts who could choose the best way of addressing this. It is also in EERA's power to facilitate discussion on standards, actively promote them and supervise their implementation in a majority of wind energy research projects in Europe.

3.1.1 Data formats

Because of the multidisciplinary problems and competition between different commercial solutions, there is a countless amount of data formats used in wind energy. For example every research centre is using a combination of different Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), Computer Aided Design (CAD), Finite Element Methods (FEM), mostly commercial software with incompatible input and output. The file standards are often closed or simply "invented on demand" by the research centres. This has led to a situation where the typical file formats used for data exchanged are text (usually some variation of CSV), Excel or Matlab files. In some situations (for example: CFD mesh, flow field, orography) more than one format has to be provided as some of the researchers do not have access to the software required to use the file. A large part of "everyday work" of wind energy researchers is writing scripts which convert text files to the needed format. This situation causes separation and duplication of research efforts.

Specific file formats need to be agreed on and encouraged/enforced. Software for file conversion should be open source and shared. Encouraged file formats should be open and self describing, and the creation of new formats should be discouraged.

A perfect example of a file format which is already well known in the wind energy community is NetCDF. There is a general agreement (among the scientists who used it before) that NetCDF, by design is very flexible and together with CF Convention could easily replace (and be superior to) most of the file formats currently in use.

Worth noting here is also the FUSED-Wind project, which worked on input/output standards for wind energy engineering models (wind farm flow and cost, wind turbine codes). The details of FUSED-Wind developments should be reviewed in this context.

3.1.2 Metadata

There are three metadata schemas that should be considered here:

- **descriptive** - general description, taxonomy, variable types and meaning,
- **structural** - relations with other data sets, publications,
- **administrative** - access rights, location.

3.1.2.1 Descriptive metadata

The high level taxonomies are necessary in order to classify and filter data sources. This allows a better estimation of data needs for the wind energy community and makes the data discoverable outside of the small community for which it was created. The standardization work on higher level taxonomies should be discussed with the communities dealing with data sharing and publishing in general (libraries, [EUDAT](#), [OpenAIRE](#), [RDA](#) or [DataCite](#)) as well as with large wind energy data providers ([NEWA](#), [A2e](#)).

Lower level (more specific) taxonomies by categorization, allow data mining and comparison of research results. A good example of those are taxonomies created for categorization of models and benchmarks within IEA [Wakebench](#) and IRPWind WP6 projects.

Finally, the descriptive data should allow precise understanding of the file format and the numerical data provided. The best example of this is [CF Conventions and Metadata](#). It is clear that any planned work on metadata for wind energy should be based on CF metadata and extend it to address aspects not covered by the Climatology and Forecasting community.

Proposed actions for standardisation
NetCDF files following (where possible) CF conventions, will be introduced at the benchmarking activities within IRPWind and IEA projects. Scripts which convert other formats to NetCDF will be publically shared.
A project will be defined where general purpose solution will be developed for automatic or semi-automatic post-processing and plotting tools of standardised NetCDF files.
A project will be defined where high level metadata (administrative and taxonomies) for wind energy data will be developed.
EERA will maintain and, where possible, enforce data and metadata standards for wind energy.

3.1.2.2 Structural metadata

Structural metadata allows the construction of a relationship graph representing the connections between data sources, authors, funding agencies, projects, and research institutions. Once the graph is constructed it is possible to improve functioning of search engines and analyze the performance of researchers, projects and research centres. Based on the progress of the [OpenAIRE](#) project, soon it should be possible to make estimations on funding efficiency.

It is unnecessary for the wind energy community to try to create complete structural metadata for their research results. The community should rather cooperate with libraries and publishers by providing necessary metadata, so specialised services can later map the relations between the publications. It

should be ensured that research results are citable (for example by providing [DOI](#) for research data and software), properly cited, and metadata about publications is being harvested by external services.

A problem which can not be easily addressed occurs when trying to properly publish data, as the available solutions are either at national level [\[7\]](#) or are for open access only ([ZENODO](#), [EUDAT](#), [GigaDB](#)). This results in a reduced visibility of research results from the wind energy community in platforms such as [OpenAIRE](#) ([Figure 1](#)). There is a need for a repository for wind energy, where data, software and publications could be registered. The repository would serve as:

- metadata source for [OpenAIRE](#) and other search engines,
- search engine for wind energy community
- [DOI](#) generator for data stored in wind energy databases.

Proposed actions for data publishing
Consider IRPWind infrastructures call, for projects “enabling” existing physical infrastructures within the European e-infrastructure.
Find a solution for generating Data Object Identifiers for data generated by wind energy community.

3.1.2.3 Administrative metadata

Administrative metadata is related to Data Management Plans, which are already obligatory in H2020 projects. This aspect is covered by the next section [3.2](#) Legal.

3.2 Legal

Similar to standardisation, common e-infrastructures can not exist without clearly addressing the legal aspects of data and services exchanged within it. Also, as in the case of defining new standards, EERA is the most qualified organisation in Europe to address the topic in a way that would fit the reality of wind energy research and enforce the use of selected legal solutions.

Currently the typical scenario for defining a legal framework for research is project based. Legal departments of institutions (or the whole consortium) define legal documents for the project participants to sign and send them via email. Each project participant reviews the documentation with its own legal department and negotiates the changes. Once an agreement is reached, signed documents are send back to the data provider. The process of gaining access to data, depending mostly on the number of institutions that have to agree to share their resources, takes from a couple of months to years and is not always successful. This makes the process of sharing the research data expensive and unpredictable and, as expected, makes the data providers reluctant to cooperate. Data are usually shared for the duration of the project with a verbal assurance that it will become public “later”. Sometimes when it is considered old enough, data is simply shared by e-mail without any license whatsoever.

Proposed actions for licensing
Creation of standard licenses for different data accessibility levels, preventing wasting efforts on NDA negotiations and using clauses which are illegal for public institutions.

Definition of a template EERA Data Management Plan which includes EERA policies, promotes data standards, publication channels and mechanisms for long-term data preservation. The EERA DMP should be the main instrument to ensure the applicability of EERA policies in EU research projects.

Data sharing is one of the key issues within the wind energy community and data management plans with standard licenses could address that in many levels. The process would be faster and cheaper, as well as funding agencies would have written commitments from the beginning of the project which they could enforce even after the project is long finished. Finally, well defined data management plans include the description of metadata generation process, addressing the common issue in which the data are only accessed by the scientists who generated it, as only they know how to use it.

3.2.1 Open science

To protect their investment and to improve the efficiency of research, EC is establishing the open science as the default approach for european research [1]. There are many fears and doubts expressed within the community in regards to open science. Most of them could be solved by the correct use of Data Management Plans, or improving the use of publishing methods to deal with the lack of endorsement for research data. Also, the word “open” is often misunderstood in this context as being “accessible to anyone”.

Working with sensitive data, which is often generated by industry, is not unique to wind energy community. A good example of the above is the biomedical research, where data is sensitive, private funding is heavily involved, competition between research institutions is fierce and finally there is heavy pressure from the public for sharing. Some of the solutions used there could be easily translated to wind energy community needs.

Best practices and guidelines for Open science

“Open data” does not have to, and sometimes even should not be shared with anyone, but rather be restricted to researchers specialised in the field who will know how to correctly interpret it and how to use it in a responsible way.

Sensitive data should be available only to a very small group of researchers, who understand the dangers of sharing it as is. The group should then process the data to a form that is useful for researchers but is no longer sensitive.

Data should always be traceable to the source, ensuring that the efforts of data providers are accounted for and research results are replicable.

Similar to the medical industry, the wind energy industry is highly competitive but, happily for wind energy, certain restrictions or delays in the sharing of research results are not causing human deaths. This gives the community certain flexibility that should be considered. There is no doubt that EC funded research should be shared between the European partners, but it should also be considered that one of the impacts expected from the research projects is the “creation of jobs and boosting growth”, which in this case should be understood as “supporting of the European wind energy industry”. In the author's opinion, research which is co-sponsored by both public and private funding should be open for European

scientists and to those partners outside of the European Union which are also sharing their knowledge with the European scientific community.

3.2.2 Open access in IRPWind

IRPWind project, in accordance with the Open Science philosophy has agreed to the OpenAccess mandate consisting of the need to store all the peer-reviewed publications and providing open access to them. Unfortunately, only four indicative person-months were assigned for the project website and the space for storing the technical documents. This is not enough for developing a proper publishing platform, which in turn results in a very limited visibility of the IRPWind project [Figure 1].

OpenAIRE

PARTICIPATE SEARCH

IRPWIND SC39

Title	Integrated Research Programme on Wind Energy
Funding	EC FP7 SP1 ENERGY
Call	FP7-ENERGY-2013-IRP
Contract (GA) number	609795
Start Date	2014/03/01
End Date	2018/02/28
Open Access mandate	yes
Special Clause 39	yes
Organizations	SINTEF ENERGI AS, NTNU, UST, CNR, TUBITAK, MRTK, IREC, VTT, ECN, AAU, CIRCE, CIEMAT, KAPE - CRES, UoA, CTC, CENTRO NACIONAL DE ENERGIAS RENOVABLES CENER, KENNISCENTRUM WMC, Fraunhofer, EWEA, LUH, TECNALIA, DTU, LNEG, Uni Oldenburg
More information	Detailed project information (CORDIS)

Publications (2) Research Data (0) Statistics

Tailoring the design of a trailing edge sub-component test 3
 (2016)
 Projects: [EC | IRPWIND \(609795\)](#)

The new design guidelines promote the implementation of structural sub-component testing in the wind turbine rotor blade design certification process. These could enhance the structural reliability and augment the structural optimization of the rotor blade segments or components along the blade span. Moreover, design changes or even local repairs can be evaluated and re-certified while avoiding the full-scale test costs. In the current study, a generic tailoring procedure is introduced for th...

Input-output signal selection for damping of power system oscillations using wind power plants 8
 (2014)
 Projects: [EC | IRPWIND \(609795\)](#), [EC | IDE4L \(608860\)](#)

Figure 1. Visibility of IRPWind project in OpenAIRE [8]

IRPWind project could improve that by reviewing the dissemination levels of its deliverables. Redefine “private”, “project restricted” or any other custom dissemination level used so far, to temporarily restricted (with embargo date). Use well defined licenses for defining access rights to the documents (for example [Creative Commons](#)). And finally, either store their deliverables in [ZENODO](#) platform (as suggested in the H2020 guidelines [\[9\]](#), or at least cooperate with their libraries for referencing the documents in the publication registries. Based on the very small number of publications currently related to the IRPWind project, it can be suspected that the project results, when published are not properly referenced to IRPWind. Researchers should be aware of that and should ensure their work is endorsed.

Best practices and guidelines for IRPWind - part of the EERA Data Management Plan template
Technical deliverables in EERA projects should be public by default.
In the future EERA should use portals like ZENODO for publishing the deliverables.
Technical deliverables from EERA projects which are restricted, should still be published in ZENODO with embargo date after which it will be automatically published.

Proposed actions for IRPWind
Review dissemination levels in WP 6,7 and 8 of IRPWind changing, where possible, from restricted to public.

The approach described above guarantees to improve IRPWind visibility, dissemination and knowledge sharing. It also ensures compliance with the open access mandate and improves the impact of the project.

3.3 Infrastructure

The creation of a common e-infrastructure for research is not a new idea. There are many fields of science which have been developing and using those for years. The wind energy community is in a comfortable position where it can build on its experience and use the technical solutions which were already developed and had enough time to mature. At the same time wind energy researchers, because of their limited experience with modern e-infrastructures, should refrain from reinventing the existing solution and focus on seeking help, training and spending extra time on planning. As a rule of thumb it should be assumed that all the building blocks already exist and all the technical problems have already been solved. In fact, the difficulty here might be that too many “as good” examples can be found addressing the same topics.

Therefore, the suggested solution here is to try to achieve compatibility with the e-infrastructures which we know will be interconnected with the wind energy e-infrastructure, that is [A2e/DAP](#), [MaRINET](#) and the [European e-infrastructures](#). Wind energy researchers are already getting involved in the extension of MaRINET project - MaRINET2. One of the focuses of MaRINET2 will be adapting it to cooperate with the european e-infrastructure. Preliminary conversations with the A2e/DAP representatives which took place during this project, also showed their interest in making their resources accessible through the European e-infrastructures services. A clear conclusion here is that wind energy community should strive for maximum compatibility, and reuse of the European services.

“[...] the following best practices should be taken into account:

- Check existing e-Infrastructures and related services before defining the ICT infrastructure for your research infrastructure;
- Check with existing RIs how they realized their ICT infrastructure;
- Contact existing e-Infrastructures and ESFRI projects at national level and/or European level as appropriate;
- Work to an ICT synergy with other projects to encourage the development of the e-Infrastructure commons. This can include participation in the discussions of the interoperability framework, in the research infrastructure disciplinary field and the generic one, to make sure that your specific requirements are taken into account;
- [...]

Best Practices for the use of e-Infrastructures by large-scale research infrastructures. e-IRG [10]

Trying to define in detail the technical aspects of a wind energy e-infrastructure within this work would go against the earlier advice of “spending extra time on planning”, as well as similar guidelines coming from the [e-IRG Guidelines Document \[10\]](#). Nevertheless, a general approach and specific collaboration partners can be pointed out. Each member of EERA should join [GEANT](#) network which offers free, high speed internet infrastructure. While all the universities already have, there are still research organisations that did not join it. This is often due to IT departments (not directly related with academia) tend to have a limited knowledge about it. Databases should be interconnected with the [EUDAT](#) services. Indirectly by following their approach to data organisation and publication, or directly by cooperation, where EUDAT can offer their expertise and data storage infrastructure. [ZENODO](#) and [OpenAIRE](#) should be used or mimicked when creating a publishing and discovery e-infrastructure. Finally, all the potential elements of the wind energy e-infrastructure should support single sign-on protocols and federated architecture. In practice, this means support to SAML2 protocol ([EduGAIN](#)), though allowing other protocols like OpenID (Google, Amazon, IBM) or Facebook Connect should be considered. Federated architecture for identity control allows different levels of security and better control of where personal data are stored. Accounts for employees of industrial partners are not supported by EduGAIN, therefore a custom solution will have to be used. Both SeaDataNet and A2e/DAP use centralised identity services - Marine-id (maintained by SeaDataNet) and jumpcloud account (commercial service for A2e). Federated architecture also gives an option for private companies to maintain their own identity server, thus maintaining full control on their employees data and security.

Best practices and guidelines for e-infrastructures

Re-use existing solution, and be compatible with the European e-infrastructure services. Any project implementing e-infrastructures should reserve extra time for the planning phase.

Support protocols for single sign-on. If possible, support existing examples (Marine-id, Orchid, EduGAIN).

A new (or existing, if funding available) database project should get in contact with EUDAT, to make their data discoverable via B2FIND service to the research community.

Experimental results should be citable and discoverable, allowing their endorsement and the monitoring of their use. Lack of endorsement of experimental data is one of the reasons why they are restricted .

Research institutions should join GEANT network - the problem exists with some public research institutions which are not directly related with universities.

When it comes to the European e-infrastructure services it is important to understand their advantages and restrictions. In general they are free to use for researchers, restricted to industry and to certain degree enforce open access. This implies that the wind energy e-infrastructure might need hybrid solutions. For example:

- single sign-on - [EduGAIN](#) and [Marine-id](#) (or a new service “Wind-id”);
- publishing - [ZENODO](#), national solutions (DTU Library, CSIC-Spain) and a new wind energy specific repository;
- databases - [EUDAT](#) and existing wind energy databases.

3.4 Raising awareness

The main point of creating a common research infrastructure is to facilitate cooperation and improve research efficiency. Those targets are impossible to achieve without trust and understanding of the available solutions. Current knowledge about the existing European e-infrastructure services in wind energy research community is minimal and restricted to a small number of researchers. Also, the understanding of technical possibilities of grid computing and trust to federated identity management, is restricted only to some of the ICT specialists within academia.

Before the European wind energy community can make use, or even think of what modern ICT infrastructure has to offer, it is crucial that knowledge about it will be improved. Below a number of actions is suggested that could easily be implemented within the IRPWind project and could have great impact on the final results of the project.

Proposed actions for raising awareness

Invite e-infrastructures experts for the IRPWind conference. Maybe for the IRPWind General Assembly meeting.

Invite researchers with successful use cases to present at the IRPWind conference.

Consider IRPWind infrastructures call for projects “enabling” existing physical infrastructures within the European e-infrastructure.

4 Conclusions

Chapter [3](#) of the document provides a list actions and advices for EERA and in general to the wind energy community. Their objectives are focused on improving the knowledge on the topic and they provide a starting point for addressing the key aspects of research e-infrastructures: standardisation, legal and ICT.

A number of solutions and references is suggested for standardisation and EERA is pointed out as the best candidate for definition and maintenance of wind energy specific standards. Much attention is given the Open Science approach to research - what does it mean and how EERA could improve its support. Examples and suggestions are given for the technical aspects of e-infrastructures and finally, a number of actions is listed for improving the knowledge on the topic within the wind energy community.

Throughout the project a number of case studies for use or development of e-infrastructures have been considered. Space for improvements have been found in some of the ongoing projects, as well as in the project proposals which are being defined at the moment. The most significant output is the decision to create a small, focus group which will continue the work on some aspects of the document in more detail and under EERA's endorsement. Apart from that, the following ideas are being considered in connection to ongoing and future projects:

- making better use of the services available within the European research infrastructure,
- cross-atlantic collaboration on standardisation, and interoperability of wind energy e-infrastructures,
- adapting the long-term plans for projects, considering the idea of the European digital single market.

The project also resulted in raising awareness of the e-infrastructure topic and connected a group of researchers willing to address it.

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APPENDIX

Examples of e-infrastructure elements significant for the European wind energy community

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December 2016

In this document we present a list of examples that should be considered when designing an e-infrastructure for the European wind energy. The list is non-exhaustive but is representative of ideas and elements that should be reviewed. The document also serves as a reference for the “Towards an European e-infrastructure for wind energy” document.

Summary table

	Identity	Legal	Publishing	Database	Standardization	Institutional	Services
Marinet + Seadatanet	X	X		X	X		
A2e	X	X		X	X		
Edugain	X						
ORCID	X						
Creative Commons		X					
DOI			X				
Dat-data			X				
Docker			X				X
EUDAT			X	X	X		X
OpenAIRE					X		X
Zenodo		X	X		X		
PRACE							X
GÉANT							X
Global Atlas IRENA				X			
NEWA, Windscanner				X	X		X
Dublin Core					X	X	
NetCDF					X		
CF Convention					X		
RDA					X	X	
GigaDB				X			
re3data				X			
NREN						X	
FUSED-Wind					X		X
EGI		X		X		X	X
Windbench				X	X		
Jupyter							X

1 European e-infrastructure services

1.1 NRENs

National Research and Education Network is a group of national organisations responsible for management and operation of the local E&R networks. Each of the organisation is defined at a national level and provides internet access to the public internet infrastructure for universities and other public institutions. They also control access to .gov or .edu domains, provide digital certification and identity services. An important part of NREN's activities is the maintenance of legal compatibility between the local laws and the rules for the international e-infrastructure collaborations.

1.2 GÉANT

GÉANT is a pan-European public organisation providing networking services for organisations. The most important service it offers is **GÉANT network** - high bandwidth, high capacity backbone internet for research and education. GÉANT connects the hubs within the European infrastructure with similar networks all around the world using multiple of 100Gb/s connections. At a national level GEANT is cooperating with NREN's. Usually local NRENs are responsible for the support to local institutions and policies of who is eligible for joining the network.

GÉANT also manages identity and trust services such as eduGAIN and eduroam.

EduGAIN is a federated identity service allowing single-sign-on and use of other services provided through GÉANT and other related networks. EduGAIN consists of over 2200 identity providers serving 50 million users. At a technical level EduGAIN allows each user to obtain a certificate from his identity provider, confirming his identity and affiliation. The certificate is then trusted by the global R&E network allowing the user to request resources or services.

Eduroam is a simple but very popular and practical example of the use of eduGAIN, where researchers can access wifi in other member institutions, using their home institution login and password.

Figure 1. GÉANT topology at October 2015

http://www.geant.org/Networks/Pan-European_network/Pages/GEANT_topology_map.aspx

1.3 PRACE

Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe is a non-profit association of 25 member countries, which provides access to six world class HPC services. Access to PRACE resources can have two forms:

- Preparatory access - short term access intended for testing the scalability of the code, its adaptation to the specific HPC infrastructure and improvement of performance.
- Project access - 1-3 year production runs.

Projects eligible for PRACE support have to show “[...] very high scientific quality and with a broad European scope, importance and relevance.” <http://www.prace-ri.eu/prace-in-a-few-words/> and have to pass the scientific review process.

The use of PRACE resources is free and the professional ICT support is covered by the PRACE funding.

1.4 EUDAT

Is a provider of comprehensive data services for european research and education users. It includes a short term storage close to the HPC centres, private storage for joint research (service similar to dropbox), long term storage for open scientific data and a data discovery service.

Basic services are available to any european researcher. Services where stronger support or large amount of storage is necessary, can be accessed through yearly data-calls. Being a new service, the distinction between basic and advanced services has not yet been fully defines

Data stored in EUDAT are expected to be properly described using metadata and open (though sensitive data can be restricted only to specific scientific communities). Use of EUDAT is free for research and education. This includes commercial partners working with research institutions and willing to share their scientific results coming from the project.

Figure 2. B2DROP service tested - 20GB limit with 4MB/s upload speed.

1.5 OpenAIRE

The main purpose of OpenAIRE is to collect metadata about publications from other platforms, join, enrich and clean them. When it comes to search engine for scientific publications, compared with more mature services like Google Scholar, OpenAIRE at first seems to have limited use for researchers. The first impressions though can be misleading. OpenAIRE database consists of well structured metadata (not just text search), possibility of custom database queries (beta stage as of 10-2016) and information about project and funding agency related to publications.

This shows the real reason for the creation of OpenAIRE whose database is a perfect tool for funding agencies for estimating the impact of research projects they are supporting. Custom queries also allow the development of services for live information on impact of research (projects, scientists, publication, experiments), or notification services (for example on publications based on specific experimental results). In short, in contrast to other similar search engines, OpenAIRE is focused on the better traceability of research and control of funding.

1.6 ZENODO

OpenAire also maintains a publication platform zenodo, allowing researchers to publish their work free of charge. By supporting precise and complete metadata formats from OpenAIRE, zenodo makes publications visible for the funding agencies. While ZENODO's mission is to support the idea of open science, it allows a number of licenses restricting access to their results (license have to be defined). This comes from the understanding that in some cases the data can be sensitive and should be restricted only to a specific scientific community.

1.7 EGI

European Grid Infrastructure is a federation of 21 nacional level infrastructures, standardising and supporting their cooperation. Services offered within EGI are based on the ideas of grid or cloud computing and have a very broad spectrum. The grid middleware facilitates security (based on federated approach) and efficiency of communication. On top of that a large number of services is accessible, which are usually tailor made for specific use cases.

Grid infrastructure allows seamless and secure use of interconnected machines. In practice it often consists of a large number of desktop machines connected by "standard" networking solutions - in contrast to HPC machines which offer very fast internal communication. Having access to large amount of desktop machines, where in general only a fraction of the accessible computing power is used, grid computing allows access to large computing and storage resources with no investment and minimal maintenance costs. Another powerful use case is the ability to provide access to internal resources to specific users from other trusted institutions.

Grid infrastructure is an all-purpose solution. The drawback of the flexibility is that it has to be supported at an institutional level and needs specialised knowledge to set-up. While people with the right experience are usually available at universities, this could be problematic in other research centres or private companies. Also the use of grid infrastructure (unless an interface for the specific solution is developed) requires basic understanding of how it operates.

In wind energy community, grid infrastructure could be used to build elements of potential research e-infrastructure, but should not be considered as out-of-the-box solution or a tool that could be used by single researchers without the support of the IT department within his institution.

1.8 ORCID

ORCID is a European non-profit organisation providing unique identifications numbers for researchers. In contrast to user accounts provided by EduGAIN, it is not focused on providing access to resources (which can change over time for example when researchers change affiliation), but is rather focused on referencing the scientific accomplishments of a specific person. ORCID can be compared to DOI but

instead of pointing to digital objects, reference a specific researcher in a unique and persistent way. The relation can be perfectly seen in the ODIN project <https://odin-project.eu/> ORCID support federated login protocols. It is also an official repository of researchers used at the national levels within the EU.

1.9 European Cloud Partnership - The Digital Single Market

There is currently work being done on providing legal, standardisation and infrastructure layer for commercial services. Commercial services would be accessed through NREN's, would be standardised and compatible with national regulations. The private infrastructure would be connected to GEANT network, thus ensuring seamless connection speed with the existing research and education infrastructure. The services, by being offered by NREN's could be accessed without the need for public procurements (call for services would be defined at the European level). The approach is to reduce costs of research by gaining access to cheap, large scale, commercial solutions. First commercial services should be available within 2-3 years.

<https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-cloud-partnership>

2 Wind energy related services

2.1 MaRINET + SeaDataNet

Marine Renewables Infrastructure Network (MaRINET) and Pan-European Infrastructure for Ocean and Marine Data Management (SeaDataNet) are two key projects responsible for the creation of infrastructure for marine and ocean research. While both projects are too complex to be well described in one paragraph, for the purpose of the document they can be described as, MaRINET being focused on the physical infrastructure and renewables, while SeaDataNet taking care of the e-infrastructure connecting them and other ocean data sources.

Work on the SeaDataNet e-infrastructure started in 2006 and was continued until 2015. MaRINET project was implemented in 2010-2012 and its extension has been accepted for years 2017-2022. As the scope of both of the project is overlapping with some of the offshore activities of wind energy research community, they should be carefully considered when designing a wind energy e-infrastructure.

Especially worth reviewing is the work done on the standardisation within SeaDataNet. Similar to A2e, for general-purpose standard, SeaDataNet choose to use NetCDF file formats with CF convention, but they also decided to extend the CF convention with additional metadata definition. Below is a brief summary of the used standards.

- File formats
 - SeaDataNet ODV4 ASCII for profiles, time series and trajectories,
 - SeaDataNet NetCDF with CF compliance for profiles, time series and trajectories,
 - SeaDataNet MedAtlas as optional extra format,
 - NetCDF with CF compliance for [3D observation data such as ADCP](#).
 - http://www.seadatanet.org/content/download/16251/106283/file/SDN2_D85_WP8_Datafile_formats.pdf
- meta databases and data formats
 - NERC Vocabulary Server
 - http://www.bodc.ac.uk/products/web_services/vocab/ .

- XML for metadata
 - <http://www.seadatanet.org/Standards-Software/Metadata-formats>

Finally, the standards are complemented with Data Quality Control procedures.

[http://www.seadatanet.org/content/download/18414/119624/file/SeaDataNet_QC_procedures_V2_\(May_2010\).pdf](http://www.seadatanet.org/content/download/18414/119624/file/SeaDataNet_QC_procedures_V2_(May_2010).pdf)

SeaDataNet is implementing a single-sign-on protocol (LDAP) with a centralised server maintaining user accounts (marineID)

(http://www.seadatanet.org/content/download/9749/65717/file/sdn_tech_Authentication_Services_Manual_1.2.pdf). This architecture will be extended to the federated identity within MaRINET 2 project which will recognise EduGAIN users. By supporting the LDAP protocol SeaDataNet ensured that the future extensions of the e-infrastructure will be possible, thus allowing MaRINET2 project to focus on adding to existing services rather than re-implementing the whole e-infrastructure.

2.2 Global Atlas for Renewable Energy (IRENA)

The Global Atlas for Wind Energy - initiative coordinated by IRENA (International Renewable Energy Agency) - is a repository of over 1000 distributed datasets. The datasets have been contributed by more than 50 institution. While not all the datasets can be downloaded through the Global Atlas, they all can be visualised using the online GIS tool. The visualisation tool can also be used with custom data sources supporting OGC (open geospatial) standard

<http://globalatlas.irena.org/default.aspx>

2.3 NEWA, Windscanner

The New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) is a project which will develop a new, high fidelity, wind resource atlas for Europe, along with the state of the art process for wind resource assessment. <http://euwindatlas.eu/index.html> Windscanner is an [ESFRI](#) (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure) supported project focused on a new technology for the 3-dimensional wind-flow measurements using LIDAR technology. <http://www.windscanner.eu>

Aside from the actual European wind atlas (which will be published in IRENA Global Atlas or Global Wind Atlas <http://globalwindatlas.com/map.html>), the two project will collaborate on the database for the measurement campaigns. Windatlas will be used in most of the test sites planned for NEWA, and the measurements will be stored in a distributed (national nodes) database. Most likely the same database will be used for related (met-mast, weather forecast) data generated in the field experiments of the NEWA project. Both of the projects will include some work on data standardisation. NEWA will publish a number of open source modelling tools (WRF, OpenFOAM, CFD meshing), thus creating a reference model-chain.

The two projects together, are a perfect starting points for the creation of a wind energy e-infrastructure. Unfortunately, while they address many elements of a potential e-infrastructure it is not their main target and as follows, the planned e-infrastructure lacks in the necessary scope, compatibility with other e-infrastructures and long term planning. It is crucial that the both projects are aligned with a potential e-infrastructure project as soon as possible, while they are still at an early stage of development.

2.4 A2e Data Archive and Portal (DAP)

A2e is a large, integrated research initiative for wind energy in the US, focused on improving the performance and reliability of wind farms. It is funded by the Department of Energy and in general it could be compared to the IRPWind project in the EU. The key part of the A2e project in the context of this document is the Data Archive and Portal (DAP). Being work in progress, there is currently limited information available on the project. Nevertheless, after contacting the researchers related to the project the following observations were made:

- In the coming year A2e will be working on high level taxonomies for data, to make them easier to discover and filter.
- By 2022 the objective is to develop tools for data processing, visualization, data mining, etc.
- A2e is very open to collaboration and interested in sharing data through EUDAT (European data e-infrastructure service).
- NetCDF file with CF Convention was chosen as a standard for all stored data (with some exceptions for GRIB format).
- Users aren't expected to provide the files in the right format but instead, by default, all the files are converted to NetCDF by the A2e/DAP team. Support level depends on a project. Some datasets are verified in terms of the A2e standards guidelines, some are not. Sometimes only the standard and guidance is provided and the data isn't reviewed. No data is rejected when the standards are not followed.
- It takes time and is challenging to understand raw data. There are issues with data duplicates, file naming conventions (needed for attaching the files to the right project), empty files...
- Amazon is used for general storage, while A2e data servers are used for large datasets.
- 2-factor authentication is used for proprietary data, scp access.
- DOI are generated for all the stored datasets.
- Conversion tools for NetCDF, which are being used/developed, are available online.
- There are difficulties in making changes to CF Convention official. It hasn't been decided yet how to resolve it, but creation of separate branch of the convention might be necessary.

wfip2 / mbr.z01.00

Microbarograph • ESRL Hi-Res Microbarograph, Boardman • Raw Data

Purpose

20 Hz sample rate of pressure (mb) at surface.

Data Quality

Not provided

Uncertainty

Not provided

Constraints

Not provided

References

Not provided

More Information

ASCII Format

- Field 1: DataloggerID
- Field 2: Year
- Field 3: Julian Day
- Field 4: Hour and Min (UTC)
- Field 5: Seconds Decimal (UTC)
- Field 6: GPS Lock Identifier (A = Locked Signal; V=Insufficient satellite coverage)
- Field 7: GPS Clock String (UTC)

Data Summary & Access

Dataset Name	wfip2/mbr.z01.00
DOI	10.21947/1328940
File Type(s)	txt
File Count	2,800
Total Size	11 GB
Start Date	2016 07 21
End Date	2016 11 23

i Last updated **3 minutes** ago.

Click to highlight, Ctrl+C (on Mac, Cmd+C) to copy URL

<sftp://download.a2e.energy.gov/wfip2/mbr.z01.00/>

i [Login](#) to find your user ID that will be needed to access the download area.

Data download is via read-only SFTP, which may require [additional software](#).

In order to provide automated access, you can also configure SSH keys as part of your [JumpCloud account](#).

Figure 3. A2e example data package <https://a2e.pnnl.gov/data/wfip2/mbr.z01.00>

2.5 FUSED-Wind + OpenMDAO

“Framework for Unified Systems Engineering and Design of Wind Plants (FUSED-Wind) is a free open-source framework for multi-disciplinary optimisation and analysis (MDAO) of wind energy systems, developed jointly by the Wind Energy Department at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU Wind Energy) and the National Renewable Laboratory (NREL).”

<http://www.fusedwind.org/>

OpenMDAO is a powerful, statistical tool which can analyze the relation between inputs and outputs of engineering models. With enough sampling data MDAO can predict how certain choices of the model

settings influence the quality of the models results. FUSED-Wind makes use of that by interfacing wind energy models (wind farm flow and cost, wind turbine codes) with the OpenMDAO libraries. The most important aspect of the project in relation to wind energy e-infrastructures, is the data standardization for the input/output of the models. Extending and disseminating of the standards could greatly reduce the time-to-market and competitiveness of engineering models used in wind energy. In connection with the idea of e-infrastructures, FUSED-Wind would lead to the rapid improvement to existing models, as well as creation of cloud based market of commercial services for wind energy.

2.6 Windbench

Windbench.net is a verification and validation (V&V) platform, developed to store repositories of models, model benchmarks and benchmarking results. The ambition of windbench is to guide wind energy model developers and end-users on best practices for the evaluation of models. Windbench has so far been used for intercomparison of models for wake, wind flow over complex terrain, WT aerodynamic and structure. In each case best practice guidelines were being defined ensuring quality results which are both reproducible and comparable. Windbench also offers hosting for project websites and supports various access control rules.

Figure 4. V&V workflow <http://windbench.net/>

3 Other

3.1 Creative Commons

Creative Commons (CC) is a set of licenses which could be used for publicly shared research results. The largest advantage of use of CC is that it is in general well known and understood and the sense behind of the legal definition of each of the licenses, can be easily specified in few clear sentences. There are six available options of the license which can be distinguished by two questions:

Allow adaptations of your work to be shared?

- Yes
- No
- Yes, as long as others share alike

Allow commercial uses of your work?

- Yes
- No

In all cases the license demands and specifies the way of attribution.

<https://creativecommons.org>

3.2 DOI

DOI stands for Digital Identifier of an Object. DOI is unique and persistent. It is managed by a not-for-profit organisation and a federation of registration agencies through which the DOI is assigned. DOI consists of three short numbers (for example 10.1000/182) which can be resolved with an URL (for example, <https://doi.org/10.1000/182>) which in turn forwards to the object that it is identifying. The main difference between URL and DOI is that DOI points to an object whose location (URL) might change in the future. The metadata of the DOI can be changed at any time.

<https://www.doi.org/>

The leading DOI provider for research is DataCite. Some members of IRPWind should be able to generate DOI's through national DataCite members (DTU, TUDelft, CSIC-Spain, British Library, BIBSYS-Norway), but there is no single organisation that could be used for automatic "minting" of DOI's for wind energy community.

<https://www.datacite.org/members.html>

Zenodo and EUDAT generate DOI's for objects published there, but they are restricted to open access data only.

3.3 Jupyter

Jupyter notebook is a web interface for creating documents which interlap text and runnable code. By making it work through the browser the code could easily be shared and published. As a consequence, Jupyter allows publication of fully reproducible scientific results. A good example showing the possibilities of the approach is a notebook that was published as a support to the “[Warming Ocean Threatens Sea Life](#)” article.

Figure 5. Example plot generated using Jupyter

<http://www.scientificamerican.com/article.cfm?id=warming-ocean-threatens-sea-life>

Dealing with a topic in which there exists a certain level of distrust to scientific publications, the author provides fully reproducible results, based on data coming directly from the source.

```
In [1]: %bash
if [ ! -f sst.mean.nc ]; then
  wget ftp://ftp.cdc.noaa.gov/Datasets/coads/2degree/enh/sst.mean.nc 2>/dev/null
fi
if [ ! -f sst.stddev.nc ]; then
  wget ftp://ftp.cdc.noaa.gov/Datasets/coads/2degree/enh/sst.stddev.nc 2>/dev/null
fi
```

Figure 6. Code in Jupyter used to download data files from the source for later processing.

http://nbviewer.jupyter.org/github/robertodealmeida/notebooks/blob/master/scientific_american/Scientific%20American%20graph.ipynb

The interesting aspects of this example are that the generated plot can be at any time refreshed with the latest, updated data, or a different data source can be used. Also the provided scripts are relatively simple as Jupyter supports well the NetCDF format (.nc files).

3.4 Docker

Docker is a new approach to software virtualisation where, while by default software package is fully sandboxed, it is mostly using the libraries of the host operating system. The docker packages are (in comparison to full virtualisation approach) extremely lightweight and by default are always deployed

stateless, using only single use, virtual hard drives. Docker is implemented in Linux, but with the use of Virtual Box software, docker can be deployed on any operating systems (the image is only 40MB) and is well supported by the cloud service providers (<https://aws.amazon.com/ecs/>). Docker comes with a build in package distribution mechanism allowing easy publishing and sharing of software. The distribution mechanism is integrated with github.

In practice docker allows deployment of complex packages with all the necessary environment using a single command. For example jupyter package which includes Python with a number of libraries, web server and jupyter server can be run with a single command:

```
docker run jupyter/scipy-notebook
```

The command will download and deploy all necessary packages on top of the docker core and will make jupyter accessible through the browser.

Figure 7. Deploying jupyter server in the local network using docker.

3.5 GigaDB

GigaDB is a data repository hosting publically available data sets. Mostly the stored data are related to articles published in GigaScience journal. GigaDB is a good example of how data should be published.

<http://gigadb.org/>

Data released on September 20, 2016

Supporting data for "Analyzing climate variations on multiple timescales can guide Zika virus response measures"

Muñoz, G; Thomson, M, C; Goddard, L; Aldighieri, S (2016): Supporting data for "Analyzing climate variations on multiple timescales can guide Zika virus response measures" GigaScience Database. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5524/100243> [RIS](#) [BIBTeX](#) [TEXT](#)

The emergence of Zika virus (ZIKV) as a public health emergency in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) occurred during a period of severe drought and unusually high temperatures. Speculation in the literature exists that these climate here we provide the data upon which we based our interpretations. As described in the manuscript these have been acquired from the full data, which are available at <http://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/maproom/Health/index.html> and http://datoteca.ole2.org/maproom/Sala_de_Salud-Clima/index.html.es

Contact Submitter

Related manuscripts:

doi: [10.1186/s13742-016-0146-1](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13742-016-0146-1)

Additional information:

<http://iridl.ldeo.columbia.edu/maproom/Health/index.html>

http://datoteca.ole2.org/maproom/Sala_de_Salud-Clima/index.html.es

Files: (FTP site) Table Settings

File Name	Sample ID	File Type	File Format	Size	Release Date	
p_anom.nc		NetCDF	UNKNOWN	1.77 KB	2016-09-06	↓
p_decadal.nc		NetCDF	UNKNOWN	3.68 KB	2016-09-06	↓
p_interannual.nc		NetCDF	UNKNOWN	3.68 KB	2016-09-06	↓

Figure 8. Example data from GigaDB <http://dx.doi.org/10.5524/100243>

3.6 Dat-data

Dat-data is an interesting approach for a “zero-cost” solution for sharing data. It allows easy file sharing using a peer-to-peer (P2P) approach, but in contrast to standard P2P solution the shared data (folders) can be edited and versioning is supported. An advantage over a typical cloud/centralised server approach for file sharing is that by using P2P approach, it is free and scalable. Also an interesting feature is that it supports random access to files (only the necessary part of the file needs to be downloaded before it can be used).

Dat-data needs to be used with care as once published and synchronised with someone else, the data can not be removed. Also dat-data works better the more peers have local copies of the shared files. It will not work efficiently for large data stored in a small number of machines as the synchronisation speed will be slow, large files will be copied many times and the files will only be accessible when at least one of the peers machine is online.

3.7 RDA

“The Research Data Alliance (RDA) is an international organization focused on the development of infrastructure and community activities aimed to reduce barriers to data sharing and exchange, and promote the acceleration of data driven innovation worldwide.”

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

Within Europe, RDA is supported under the e-infrastructure topic within H2020, and consists of members from most of the organisations responsible for the European e-infrastructures.

http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/194834_en.html

RDA so far launched two calls for collaboration projects, which in general were to provide “added value in improving data sharing and reuse”.

<https://europe.rd-alliance.org/rda-eu-opportunities/rda-collaboration-projects>

The latest call (recently closed - October 2016) expected the projects to be small (6 month, 15k eur) and co-funded. The future calls could be used as a medium for synchronising the standardization efforts for the European wind energy community with other communities and the wind energy researchers on a global scale.

3.8 Dublin Core

Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) is an organisation supporting development, innovation and maintenance of higher level metadata standards. DCMI supports collaborative work by DCMI Communities and Task Groups, and by organising conferences, meetings and workshops. By education activities it supports efforts to promote widespread acceptance of metadata standards and best practices. DCMI recommendations are widely supported by organisation dealing with content publishing.

<http://dublincore.org/>

3.9 NetCDF

NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) is a data file standard together with an extensive set of libraries to support it. The standard and the supporting libraries are fully open. The files are self described, binary, randomly accessible and support multidimensional arrays. NetCDF is superior, and could easily replace most of the file standards used today in wind energy community.

NetCDF: doi:10.5065/D6H70CW6 <http://doi.org/10.5065/D6H70CW6>

3.10 CF Conventions

CF (Climate and Forecast) conventions and metadata can be shortly characterized as low level metadata. It is the best example of the data units naming convention currently available for wind energy. The approach is to be able to describe data sets so that they are clearly understandable for both users and machines. The ambition for the naming convention is to make it complete (for climate and forecast), but avoid confusion from providing overlapping meaning.

Example 3.1. Use of standard_name

```
float psl(lat,lon) ;  
    psl:long_name = "mean sea level pressure" ;  
    psl:units = "hPa" ;  
    psl:standard_name = "air_pressure_at_sea_level" ;
```

The description in the standard name table entry for `air_pressure_at_sea_level` clarifies that "sea level" refers to the mean sea level, which is close to the geoid in sea areas.

Figure 9. CF Convention example <http://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/v1.6.0/cf-conventions.html>

CF Convention is often used together with the NetCDF files allowing their precise self describing. Proper use of the both standards allows automatic post-processing, analysis and plotting. CF Convention, to large degree could be used by wind energy community as is, and should be used as a base when developing similar, wind energy specific conventions.

<http://cfconventions.org/>

3.11 re3data

Registry of Research data Repositories (re3data) is a "global registry of research data repositories".

<http://www.re3data.org/>

Re3data is a tool suggested for finding repositories for storing research data generated in H2020 projects. http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf . Currently, for "wind energy" topic it only points to the US based repositories, showing lack of similar solutions for the EU.

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OpenEnergyInfo

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The Open Energy Information (OpenEI.org) initiative is a free, open source knowledge-sharing platform created to facilitate access to data, models, tools, and information that accelerate the transition to clean energy systems through informed decisions. Sponsored by the Department of Energy, and developed by the National Renewable Energy Lab, in support of the Open Government Initiative, OpenEI strives to make energy-related data and information searchable, accessible, useful to both people and machines

NREL: Renewable Resource Data Center

RReDC

Figure 10. Search results for “wind energy” research data repositories.
<http://service.re3data.org/search?query=wind+energy>